

Analysis of the Amino Acid Frequencies in the Receptor-Binding Domains of Six Human Coronaviruses

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ABSTRACT

The novel virus SARS-CoV-2 that causes COVID-19 is one of many human coronaviruses. These viruses use the receptor-binding domains of their spike protein to bind host receptors and enter cells. While SARS-CoV-2 uses the Angiotensin-Converting Enzyme 2 (ACE-2) receptor, other coronaviruses use different host receptors. However, little research has been conducted comparing the biochemical properties of the receptor domain across species and variants of viruses. Here, this research seeks to answer the question: How does the receptor pathway a novel coronavirus uses affect the similarity of amino acid frequencies (in %) at its receptor-binding domain (RBD) to other existing coronaviruses? Amino acid sequences of viral isolates were collected from May 2003 to August 2020 from the National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) Virus database, of which variants were sampled across six viral species. Alignment comparisons between isolates of a species and among different species were then performed. Among coronavirus species, polar uncharged amino acids were identified as uniquely conserved between species with the ACE2 pathway. The mean deviation for those viruses is 0.22%, compared to 3.33% across all six coronaviruses. This suggests the correlation of ACE-2 receptor usage with a signature biochemical distribution. These findings further present an algorithm to analyze the receptor pathway, critical amino acids, and biochemical distributions among variants for a novel coronavirus species. Further, the biochemistry of the RBDs for six human coronavirus species has been characterized, laying the groundwork for evolutionary and therapeutic research.

Keywords: Amino Acid, Receptor-Binding Domain, Genomic Analysis, SARS-CoV, SARS-CoV-2, MERS

I. INTRODUCTION

Coronaviruses cause widespread systemic diseases which threaten human health and cause economic loss. The epidemics of SARS (2003), MERS (2008), and the recent COVID-19 pandemic (2020) have made coronavirus diseases among the top five emerging diseases on the World Health Organization's watchlist (WHO, 2016). Therapeutics often target the coronavirus spike (S) protein, a large transmembrane glycoprotein which protrudes from the surface capsid. The S protein includes the S1 protein domain, which is involved in the initial recognition of the cell by the virus, a key step in infection (Hoffmann et al., 2020). A key component of the S1 domain is the Receptor Binding Domain (RBD), a short amino acid sequence that binds to a receptor of a human cell. The properties of the RBD are used to predict the infectivity of the virus by analyzing how efficient and effective the spike protein recognizes its receptor sequences (Gallagher & Buchmeier, 2001).

Amino acids found at the RBD enable host cell recognition and subsequent viral entry. Current research in

coronavirus RBDs has focused on comparing SARS-CoV-2 and SARS-CoV, the viruses responsible for COVID-19 and the 2003–2004 SARS outbreak (Lai, 2020). Wan et al. (2020) compared the 2003 SARS-CoV with SARS-CoV-2 and concluded that both employ the ACE2 receptor. By performing analyses of atomic-level interactions, they pinpointed amino acids 442, 472, 479, 480, and 487 as critical positions for efficient cross-species and human-to-human transmissions. Expanding upon Wan et al., researchers identified the structural basis for receptor recognition (Shang et al., 2020). An ACE2 binding ridge gave the virus a more compact conformation, allowing SARS-CoV-2 to bind ACE-2 with higher affinity and spread more efficiently. However, little research has explored the biochemical differences in receptor-binding domains between variants of coronaviruses. In addition, comparing species of coronaviruses outside the more virulent SARS family remains an unexplored area.

The RBDs of six human coronaviruses, namely, 229E, NL63, HKU1, SARS-CoV, MERS, and SARS-CoV-2, have been identified. Among these coronaviruses, SARS-CoV,

FIG. 1. Comparison of the standard deviation in the amino acid frequencies among six strains per coronavirus species. The amino acid frequencies of the receptor-binding domain are conserved among sampled SARS-CoV variants, but differ most among HKU1 sampled variants. Amino acid frequencies are more strongly conserved among SARS-CoV-2, SARS-CoV, and NL63, which are species that use the ACE2 receptor pathway.

SARS-CoV-2, and NL63 share the same host entry pathway, using Angiotensin Converting Enzyme 2 receptors to hijack human lung cells (Hoffman, 2020). By contrast, aminopeptidase N is the viral receptor for 229E, dipeptidyl peptidase 4 for sialic acid for HKU1 (Lim, 2016). Based on the receptors to which these coronaviruses bind, biochemical properties of their RBD sequences will vary.

Here, this research presents the characteristics of the amino acid sequence of the RBD for six human coronaviruses. Amino acid frequencies can inform secondary and tertiary protein structures of the RBD which guides diagnoses and therapeutics. The first hypothesis is that if strains of the same virus were compared, then the RBD would be conserved because mutations decrease the ability to effectively infect the host. The second hypothesis is that if coronaviruses (SARS-CoV, SARS-CoV-2, NL63) use the same receptor, then they would exhibit identical biochemical frequency distributions.

II. METHODS AND RESULTS

Variants of a coronavirus species may mutate to develop differences in the receptor-binding domain. First, variants of each of the six viral species were compared in intraspecies analysis. A total of over 6,000 internationally sequenced spike protein sequences were extracted from the National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) Virus database between May 2003 to August 2020. Five sequences were randomly sampled per trial to represent nonoverlapping geographic regions and time periods (Appendix 1).

		Amino Acid Biochemical Property				
		Nonpolar Aliphatic	Nonpolar Aromatic	Polar Uncharged	Acidic Negatively Charged	Basic Positively Charged
CoV	NL63	35.821	11.234	34.878	8.641	9.426
	SARS-CoV	35.821	11.793	33.944	9.164	9.084
	SARS-CoV-2	35.821	11.234	34.878	8.641	9.426
	229E	36.057	11.408	34.225	5.493	12.817
	HKU1	22.000	11.538	50.615	5.692	11.538
	MERS	33.472	10.126	41.423	8.284	6.695
Standard Deviation		5.555	0.577	6.639	1.621	2.124

TABLE 1. Biochemical properties of amino acids found in six coronavirus species. Polar uncharged amino acids constitute the greatest proportion of the RBD.

Each selected sequence was compared at amino acid locations 442, 472, 479, 480, and 487 because these sites were identified by Wan et. al. (2020) as critical positions for receptor binding. The isolates were then compared among other isolates selected for the species (Figure 1, Appendix 2). The variance between NL63, SARS-CoV, and SARS-CoV-2 strains at the 5 aforementioned residues is 0%, which indicates that the amino acids are 100% conserved. Amino acids leucine (L), asparagine (N), tyrosine (Y) are present at the five locations for all 15 strains of the three viruses. Across all species, the mean mutation rate or standard deviation, measuring the variation between isolates of the same species, is 0.22%. HKU1 has the greatest variability (0.68%) among the isolates, while SARS-CoV has the least (0%). While NL63, SARS-CoV, and SARS-CoV-2 had mean intraspecies variability of 0.0144%, there was 26 times more variability (0.376%) in the amino acid distribution of the remaining three coronaviruses. Overall, isolates were over 99% similar at the RBD, which is consistent with the observation that the site is a conserved site critical for highly specific host recognition.

Due to the similarity between strains, it is possible to use the representative strain to generalize to the population of all strains within a species. Interspecies analysis was then performed with the representative strain's distributions for each of the six viral species (Figure 2, Appendix 2). Serine (S) has the highest frequency for coronaviruses MERS (12.97%), NL63 (14.07%), and HKU1 (17.69%), while asparagine (N) and tyrosine (Y) are most frequent for SARS-CoV-2 (9.33%) and SARS-CoV (8.94%) respectively. The amino acids S, N, and Y, in addition to threonine (T), valine (V), and leucine (L), are present at the highest frequencies among all six viruses. These residues

are also present at the five locations for all 15 strains of the three viruses.

The 20 amino acids were further classified by five established biochemical properties based on their R groups for a broader overview of the RBD. Nonpolar aliphatic amino acids includes glycine, isoleucine, alanine, valine, leucine, methionine; nonpolar aromatic includes phenylalanine, tryptophan, tyrosine; polar uncharged includes threonine, cysteine, proline, serine, asparagine, and glutamine; acidic negatively charged includes aspartate and glutamate; basic positively charged includes lysine, arginine, and histidine. The most deviation between species' distributions occurs among polar uncharged amino acids (6.64%), which represent a mean 38.00% of the viral RBD. In addition, among coronaviruses using the ACE-2 receptor pathway, there is less variation in the frequency of polar uncharged amino acids. The mean deviation among NL63, SARS-CoV, and SARS-CoV-2 is 0.224%, in contrast to the mean deviation of 3.33% when 229E, HKU1, and MERS are included, shown in Table 1.

III. DISCUSSION

This research sought to characterize the receptor binding domain of human coronaviruses through amino acid sequence analysis and comparison. I conclude that coronavirus species (NL63, SARS-CoV, SARS-CoV-2) with the same receptor pathway (ACE2) have greater RBD similarity among specific amino acids and generalized amino acid biochemical properties. Polar uncharged amino acids were 100% conserved at critical amino acid sites, which corroborates the results of Wan et. al, 2020. The biochemical frequency distributions between NL63, SARS-CoV, SARS-CoV-2 are 99.78% similar, in contrast to 96.76% similarity between all species. Next, while polar uncharged amino acids varied greatly among non-ACE2 receptor species (6.639%), the frequency of these amino acids were just 0.440% different among the three coronaviruses which used the ACE2 pathway. Polar uncharged amino acids constitute the greatest proportion of the RBD, suggesting they may be a therapeutic target.

Hence, this research finds that the frequency of polar uncharged amino acids is both unique to a receptor and highly conserved between species using the same ACE2 pathway. The amino acid distribution can be leveraged to distinguish receptors and classify novel viruses.

Further, this research presents a sequence analysis algorithm that extracts and compares crucial residues of the RBD to predict amino acids of interest. This algorithm enables researchers to quickly identify chemical similarities between a new coronavirus and the six existing species, and can be robustly adapted with machine learning to predict

the receptor pathway best suited to the novel species. This extraction of amino acid properties can also be applied in assisting the design of three-dimensional models of host-viral interactions in therapeutic endeavors.

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APPENDIX

1. Accession Numbers, Geographic Location, and Collection Date of SARS-CoV-2, NL63, SARS-CoV Sample (n = 6)

	Accession Numbers			Spike Protein Length			Location			Date		
	NL63	SARS-2	SARS	NL63	SARS-2	SARS	NL63	SARS-2	SARS	NL63	SARS-2	SARS
1	QED88026	QJC2037 9	AFR5874 2	1356	1273	1255	China	USA: WA	USA	2019-0 8-20	2020-0 4-20	2012- 09-17
2	AGT51366	QKV363 35	AFR5867 2	1356	1273	1255	USA: Nashville, TN	USA: Washington, Yakima County	USA	2013-1 0-07	2020-0 6-19	2012- 09-17
3	AWK5993 1	QMI9113 0	AFR5872 8	1356	1273	1255	Kenya	USA: San Diego, California	USA	2018-0 5-22	2020-0 7-29	2012- 09-17
4	ARE29973	QJR8376 1	AFR5871 4	1356	1273	1255	USA	USA: VA	USA	2017-0 4-09	2020-0 5-11	2012- 09-17
5	APF29063	QLH9342 8	AAP4103 7	1356	1273	1255	Haiti	Bangladesh: Jashore	Canada: Toronto	2016-1 2-03	2020-0 7-15	2003- 05-16
6	YP_00376 7	YP_0097 24390.1	YP_0098 25051	1356	1273	1255	Amsterdam, Netherlands	China	Canada: Toronto	2004-0 3-23	2020-0 1-13	2020- 05-27

2. Amino Acid Distributions for Isolates of Six Human Coronavirues

Key:

Nonpolar, aliphatic R groups =

Polar, uncharged R groups =

Basic, positively charged R groups =

Nonpolar, aromatic R groups =

Acidic, negatively charged R groups =

a. Frequency of 20 Amino Acids in 229E Spike Protein

Amino Acid (1-letter abbreviations)	Amino Acid Frequency (%)				
	Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 3	Trial 4	Trial 5
G	8.451	8.451	8.451	9.155	9.155
I	5.634	6.338	5.634	4.930	4.930
A	3.521	3.521	3.521	4.930	3.521
V	11.268	11.268	11.268	11.268	11.972
L	4.930	4.930	4.930	5.634	5.634
M	1.408	1.408	1.408	1.408	1.408
F	7.042	7.042	7.042	7.746	7.042
W	1.408	1.408	1.408	1.408	1.408
Y	2.113	4.225	2.113	2.817	2.817
T	5.634	5.634	5.634	5.634	5.634
C	4.225	4.225	4.225	4.225	4.225
P	6.338	7.042	6.338	5.634	6.338
S	8.451	7.746	8.451	9.155	7.746
N	8.451	7.746	8.451	9.155	9.155
Q	1.408	1.408	1.408	0.704	0.704
D	3.521	3.521	3.521	3.521	3.521
E	2.113	2.113	2.113	1.408	2.113
K	7.042	6.338	7.042	5.634	5.634
R	2.113	2.113	2.113	2.817	3.521
H	4.930	3.521	4.930	2.817	3.521

b. Frequency of 20 Amino Acids in HKUI Spike Protein

Amino Acid (1-letter abbreviations)	Amino Acid Frequency (%)				
	Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 3	Trial 4	Trial 5
G	3.846	3.077	3.846	3.846	3.846
I	3.846	3.077	3.846	3.846	3.846
A	2.308	3.846	3.846	3.846	3.846
V	10.000	5.385	5.385	5.385	5.385
L	5.385	4.615	4.615	4.615	4.615
M	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
F	3.846	3.846	3.846	3.846	3.846
W	1.538	1.538	1.538	1.538	1.538
Y	6.154	6.154	6.154	6.154	6.154
T	4.615	6.923	6.923	6.923	6.923
C	9.231	9.231	9.231	9.231	9.231
P	7.692	7.692	7.692	7.692	7.692
S	15.385	17.692	17.692	17.692	17.692
N	8.462	8.462	8.462	8.462	8.462
Q	1.538	1.538	1.538	1.538	1.538
D	6.154	3.846	3.846	3.846	3.846
E	0.769	1.538	1.538	1.538	1.538
K	3.846	3.846	3.846	3.846	3.846
R	3.077	4.615	4.615	4.615	4.615
H	2.308	3.077	3.846	3.846	3.846

c. Frequency of 20 Amino Acids in NL63 Spike Protein

Amino Acid (1-letter abbreviations)	Amino Acid Frequency (%)				
	Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 3	Trial 4	Trial 5
G	6.047	6.047	5.973	6.121	6.047
I	5.752	5.973	5.752	5.826	5.826
A	5.678	5.678	5.678	5.605	5.605
V	9.292	9.292	9.440	9.292	9.292
L	9.735	9.661	9.808	9.735	9.735
M	0.885	0.885	0.885	0.885	0.885
F	5.531	5.605	5.605	5.605	5.678
W	0.959	0.959	0.959	0.959	0.959
Y	5.162	5.162	5.162	5.162	5.162
T	7.596	7.670	7.743	7.817	7.743
C	3.319	3.319	3.319	3.319	3.319
P	3.466	3.466	3.392	3.466	3.466
S	9.661	9.440	9.587	9.440	9.513
N	8.407	8.481	8.407	8.481	8.407
Q	4.204	4.277	4.277	4.277	4.277
D	4.204	4.130	4.130	4.130	4.130
E	2.212	2.212	2.139	2.212	2.212
K	3.171	3.097	3.171	3.097	3.171
R	3.097	3.097	2.950	3.097	3.024
H	1.622	1.549	1.622	1.475	1.549

d. Frequency of 20 Amino Acids in MERS Spike Protein

Amino Acid (1-letter abbreviations)	Amino Acid Frequency (%)				
	Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 3	Trial 4	Trial 5
G	5.439	5.439	5.439	5.858	5.439
I	4.184	4.184	4.184	4.184	4.184
A	5.021	5.021	5.021	5.021	5.021
V	7.531	7.531	7.531	7.531	7.531
L	10.042	10.042	10.042	10.042	9.623
M	1.255	1.255	1.255	1.255	1.255
F	4.184	4.184	4.184	4.184	4.603
W	0.837	0.837	0.837	0.837	0.837
Y	5.021	5.021	5.021	5.021	5.021
T	7.113	7.113	7.113	7.113	7.113
C	3.766	3.766	3.766	3.766	3.766
P	6.276	6.276	6.276	6.276	6.276
S	12.971	12.971	12.971	12.971	12.971
N	6.276	6.276	6.276	6.276	6.276
Q	5.021	5.021	5.021	5.021	5.021
D	4.184	4.184	4.184	3.766	4.184
E	4.184	4.184	4.184	4.184	4.184
K	4.603	4.603	4.603	4.603	4.603
R	1.674	1.674	1.674	1.674	1.674
H	0.418	0.418	0.418	0.418	0.418

e. Frequency of 20 Amino Acids in SARS-CoV Spike Protein

Amino Acid (1-letter abbreviations)	Amino Acid Frequency (%)				
	Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 3	Trial 4	Trial 5
G	6.295	6.295	6.295	6.295	6.295
I	6.215	6.215	6.215	6.215	6.215
A	6.693	6.693	6.693	6.693	6.773
V	7.251	7.251	7.251	7.251	7.251
L	7.888	7.888	7.888	7.888	7.888
M	1.594	1.594	1.594	1.594	1.594
F	6.614	6.614	6.614	6.614	6.614
W	0.876	0.876	0.876	0.876	0.876
Y	4.303	4.303	4.303	4.303	4.303
T	7.888	7.888	7.888	7.888	7.888
C	3.108	3.108	3.108	3.108	3.108
P	4.542	4.542	4.542	4.542	4.542
S	7.570	7.570	7.570	7.570	7.570
N	6.454	6.454	6.454	6.454	6.454
Q	4.382	4.382	4.382	4.382	4.382
D	5.817	5.817	5.817	5.817	5.817
E	3.347	3.347	3.347	3.347	3.347
K	4.781	4.781	4.781	4.781	4.781
R	3.108	3.108	3.108	3.028	3.108
H	1.195	1.195	1.195	1.195	1.195

f. Frequency of 20 Amino Acids in SARS-CoV-2 Spike Protein

Amino Acid (1-letter abbreviations)	Amino Acid Frequency (%)				
	Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 3	Trial 4	Trial 5
G	6.520	6.441	6.520	6.520	6.520
I	5.970	5.970	5.970	5.970	5.970
A	6.206	6.206	6.206	6.206	6.127
V	7.620	7.620	7.620	7.620	7.620
L	8.484	8.484	8.484	8.484	8.484
M	1.100	1.100	1.100	1.100	1.100
F	6.049	6.049	6.049	6.049	6.049
W	0.943	0.943	0.943	0.943	0.943
Y	4.242	4.242	4.242	4.242	4.242
T	7.620	7.620	7.620	7.620	7.620
C	3.142	3.142	3.142	3.142	3.142
P	4.556	4.556	4.556	4.556	4.556
S	7.777	7.777	7.777	7.777	7.855
N	6.913	6.913	6.913	6.913	6.913
Q	4.870	4.870	4.870	4.870	4.870
D	4.792	4.870	4.792	4.792	4.792
E	3.771	3.771	3.771	3.771	3.771
K	4.792	4.792	4.792	4.972	4.792
R	3.299	3.299	3.299	3.299	3.299
H	1.335	1.335	1.335	1.335	1.335